

Longitudinal Displacement of Outer Hair Cells

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ABSTRACT

The height of the organ of Corti, near incompressibility of endolymph and perilymph, and features such as the Deiters' cell phalangeal processes suggest that longitudinal displacement is relevant to the function of the cochlea. Our objective was to measure longitudinal displacements in the pillar cells (PC) and outer hair cells (OHC) at the reticular lamina surface.

Measurements were performed on ex vivo gerbil cochleae in the first turn (best frequency 30 kHz to 40 kHz, N = 5) and second turn (best frequency 2 kHz to 4 kHz, N = 4). The measurements were made simultaneously using a stroboscopic imaging technique in response to a transverse point source driving the basilar membrane from the scala tympani side. The driving frequency range was 10 Hz to 42.5 kHz, spanning greater than the range of best frequencies for the locations measured.

In both best frequency (BF) locations, the radial displacement magnitude and phase of the apex of the PC closely matched previous results of the inner hair cell stereocilia displacement¹⁵. The longitudinal component of displacement of the apex of the PC was on average 20% of the magnitude of the PC radial displacement component.

The OHC longitudinal displacement frequency response was similar to the PC radial displacement frequency response shape although it showed more spatial tuning variation at locations separated by 300 micrometers along the length of the cochlea. The magnitude at BF of the OHC longitudinal displacement was on average 70% of the magnitude of the PC radial displacement.

The results suggest that longitudinal displacement in the organ of Corti is significant and may be functional to the operation and tuning of the cochlea. The difference in longitudinal displacement of the PC and OHCs suggests that the reticular lamina is more deformable than previously thought being more susceptible to bending and shearing in-plane.

INTRODUCTION

There is increasing evidence that the vibrations of the organ of Corti in all three dimensions are relevant to the function and tuning of the cochlea. Traditionally the transverse displacement (Fig. 1) component was postulated to be the most important because it forms the surface for the scalae fluid pressure to act upon. Rigid body analysis of the anatomy of the pillar cells forming the triangular tunnel of Corti suggested that it functions to translate the transverse displacement to radial at the reticular lamina¹ (Fig. 1).

Development of more sophisticated displacement sensing systems permitted vibration analysis of the organ of Corti in the radial dimension^{2,8}. Minimally invasive techniques such as optical coherence tomography permitted more physiologically relevant measurements in intact and living cochleae⁶.

Investigations into the anatomy and structure of the cochlear partition using living and unfixed tissue revealed that the fluid spaces between the reticular lamina and the basilar membrane are larger than though based on traditional histological preparations^{3,5,14}. The presence of the Dieter's cell phalangeal processes also implies structural significance to longitudinal displacement in the organ of Corti¹⁰. It has been postulated that the fluid spaces or tunnels

may change cross section during cochlear partition deformation resulting in longitudinal fluid flow in the organ of Corti¹³. A recent study in gerbil shows evidence of longitudinal displacement in an intact cochlea⁹.

The complex displacements in the organ of Corti are hard to interpret because there are many structures resulting in many degrees of freedom. The measurement signal to noise ratio is often low and relevant displacements are in the nanometer range. We developed a system to measure displacements in the organ of Corti in response to a local stimulus. The stimulus is in the form of a blunted micropipette that can be placed on the basilar membrane to act as a point source. The advantage of an approximate point source local to the measurement location is that the response may be dominated by the point source. In an intact cochlea the response of the external, middle ear, cochlear vestibule, helicotrema, wave reflections, and other features complicates the response. Another feature is the system is capable of simultaneously measuring a two-dimensional displacement field within approximately a 200 x 300 micrometer field of view. The simultaneous measurement preserves phase relations and minimizes time varying noise and phenomena.

Figure 1. **Left:** Schematic representation of a cross section of the cochlear partition. This is the traditional slice view where transverse displacement is up and down. The green dashed line represents the cross section of the image plane of the microscope and the displacement measurements. The measurement plane projects from the line into and out of the page. The stimulus probe is placed at the foot of the outer pillar cell, and it vibrates in the transverse dimensions. **Right:** An image taken during an experiment with regions of interest overlaid on it. The shadow of the probe can be seen in the center of the image. The longitudinal direction represents moving from the base to apex with the apex toward the right side. The Pillar cells (PC) and three rows of outer hair cells (OHC1, OHC2, OHC3) are identified by the color circles as regions of interest for the image processing algorithm. In this example image, the colors of the circles (see color bar above) indicate the dominant direction of displacement. Orange and yellow indicate dominated by radial displacement and green to blue represents a smaller difference between radial and longitudinal magnitude.

METHODS

All procedures were performed at Boston University under IACUC approval. Cochleae were immediately excised postmortem from female Mongolian gerbils, and immersed in oxygenated artificial endolymph to prevent the outer hair cells from swelling⁸. The first or second turn was isolated and both the scalae were opened to allow mechanical and visual access to the cochlear partition. Refer to Zosuls 2021 for preparation methods details¹⁵.

The isolated turn preparations were mounted on an inverted microscope and positioned in a manner that resulted in the reticular lamina being in plane with the focal plane of the microscope (Fig. 1). A 20 μm diameter blunted glass pipette ‘stinger’ or displacement source was used as a probe. It was placed on the pectinate zone of the basilar membrane under the outer pillar cell foot. The probe was placed to transversely stimulate the preparation (Fig. 1, Left).

To place the probe delicately on the BM, the microscope focus was used to gauge the distance between the probe tip and the BM. The probe was advanced toward the BM with a motorized stage to ensure control as the distance was decreased. Once the two were close, the motorized stage was advanced in 500 nm steps while closely observing the BM collagen fibers for movement.

Images were captured at 8 phases of the sinusoidal mechanical stimulus using a stroboscopic imaging system described in ^{8,15}. The frequency of the stimulus was stepped from 10 Hz to 42.5 kHz to measure the frequency dependence of the cochlear structures from the stimulus.

Measurement regions of interest were tagged that corresponded to the pillar cell apex (PC) (where the outer and inner pillar cells join), and the apical surface of the outer hair cells (OHC) (Fig. 1, Right). The outer hair cells were categorized by row (OHC1, OHC2, OHC3) (Fig. 1, Right).

Two orthogonal directional edge detection convolution filters were used in cascade with a cross-correlation image tracking algorithm to calculate radial and longitudinal components of displacement of the pillar cell heads and outer hair cells. The algorithm was capable of sub-pixel displacement computation and had a noise floor of approximately 5 nm.

RESULTS

The data were pooled into first turn preparations (N=5) where the measurement was taken within 1 to 1.5 mm from the base corresponding to a best frequency (BF) range of 29 kHz to 37 kHz. The second turn data (N=4) were 6.5 to 7.5 mm from the base corresponding to a BF range of 1.5 kHz to 3 kHz. Preparations were rejected if there was

Figure 2. Pillar cell radial and longitudinal displacement frequency response in two representative experiments at different BF. Panel A and B are the magnitude and phase response of a turn 1 preparation. The data is split into regions that are basal (reverse traveling) and apical (forward traveling). Panel C and D are the magnitude and phase of a turn 2 preparation.

any damage to the Reissner's membrane, visible damage to the cells or basilar membrane, damage during probe placement, no tuning present in the frequency response, or no traveling wave present at BF frequencies. To attenuate the effect of the stinger probe locally distorting the organ of Corti, only regions of interest that were greater than 120 μm apical or basal to the probe were included in the results and calculations. Previous results indicate that this is out of the evanescent wave region of the probe ¹⁵. Since the preparation is ex vivo, the scalae are open, and the cochlea is

parted, it is assumed that the endocochlear potential is zero and the active processes have vanished. Therefore, the preparation is considered passive.

Figure 2 shows representative results of measured pillar cell radial and longitudinal displacement for pillar cells from a turn 1 and a turn 2 preparation. The results are separated into basal and apical to the probe and these regions of interest are averaged. Tuning can be seen in the radial magnitude traces of both locations in both directions. In all cases and all experiments, in the BF frequency range, the radial component of pillar cell displacement was significantly greater than the longitudinal component. The phase relation in the turn 1 data shows a $\frac{1}{4}$ cycle phase shift where the longitudinal component is leading the radial component. The turn 2 data phase did not show a consistent phase difference between radial and longitudinal components.

Figure 3 shows representative results of measured outer hair cell longitudinal displacement at both locations. The results are separated into basal and apical to the probe and into three rows of outer hair cells with OHC1 being closest to the pillar cell row. In all experiments and cases, the OHC longitudinal component of displacement showed tuning

Figure 3. Outer hair cell longitudinal displacement in the same two representative experiments as in figure 2. Panels A and B are the magnitude and phase response of the turn 1 preparation. The data is split into three rows of OHCs and basal and apical to the probe. Panels C and D are the magnitude and phase of the turn 2 experiment.

with a peak in the vicinity of the pillar cell radial component tuning. In all experiments and cases, the OHC longitudinal displacement tuning apical to the probe was observable to be lower in frequency than the basal component. This difference in apical and basal tuning was not as evident in the pillar cell radial data. In both the turn 1 and turn 2 data there was a difference in the slope of the phase response at and above the BF. In both cases the basal phase slope was greater indicating a slower reverse traveling wave relative to the forward traveling wave propagating in the apical direction.

Ratiometric comparisons of the two pools of data were calculated at the computed or observed BF for two specifications:

The first was the ratio of the magnitude of the pillar cell apex longitudinal vs. radial displacement (Fig. 4). The results suggest that the pillar cells dominant direction of displacement is radial in both turns. Not shown in the data is that the displacement patterns of an inner hair cell apical surface closely matched the displacement pattern of its adjacent pillar cell apex¹⁵.

The second ratio was the Outer hair cell longitudinal displacement vs. pillar cell apex radial displacement. The magnitude of outer hair cell longitudinal displacement is approximately 70% of the pillar cell radial displacement (Fig. 4).

DISCUSSION

The results indicate that there is a significant magnitude of longitudinal displacement in the outer hair cells. This is consistent with recent experimental results in the same species in which longitudinal displacement was measured in an intact cochlea⁹. Conversely the longitudinal displacement of the pillar cells is small.

The more pronounced apical vs. basal tuning difference in the OHC longitudinal vs. PC radial and longitudinal displacement suggests that the OHCs and PCs are sufficiently decoupled radially to permit this tuning difference. This supports results that indicate the reticular lamina is more susceptible to bending and deformation than previously thought⁴. If the reticular lamina is highly mobile, then the longitudinal connection between adjacent pillar cell heads may be the greatest contributor to the torsional stiffness of the tunnel of Corti triangle.

These results support experimental and modeling results that show mechanical significance of the Deiters' cells phalangeal processes as structures to convert displacement in the organ of Corti from transverse to longitudinal along the reticular lamina, specifically surrounding the outer hair cells, in a direction dependent manner^{10,11,12}.

Figure 4. Pooled displacement ratios with standard deviation error bars. T1 and T2 refer to turn 1 and turn 2 respectively. PCX/PCY is the ratio of the pillar cell longitudinal displacement relative to the radial displacement. OHCX/PCY is the ratio of the three rows of OHC longitudinal displacement relative to the PC radial displacement.

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REFERENCES

1. Billone, M., & Raynor, S. (1973). Transmission of radial shear forces to cochlear hair cells. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 54(5), 1143–1156. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.1914361>
2. Chan, D. K., & Hudspeth, A. J. (2005). Mechanical responses of the organ of corti to acoustic and electrical stimulation in vitro. *Biophysical journal*, 89(6), 4382–4395. <https://doi.org/10.1529/biophysj.105.070474>
3. Cho, N. H., Wang, H., & Puria, S. (2022). Cochlear Fluid Spaces and Structures of the Gerbil High-Frequency Region Measured Using Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT). *Journal of the Association for Research in Otolaryngology : JARO*, 23(2), 195–211. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10162-022-00836-4>
4. Cho, N. H., & Puria, S. (2022). Cochlear motion across the reticular lamina implies that it is not a stiff plate. *Scientific reports*, 12(1), 18715. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-23525-x>
5. Edge, R. M., Evans, B. N., Pearce, M., Richter, C. P., Hu, X., & Dallos, P. (1998). Morphology of the unfixated cochlea. *Hearing research*, 124(1-2), 1–16. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0378-5955\(98\)00090-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0378-5955(98)00090-2)
6. Fallah, E., Strimbu, C. E., & Olson, E. S. (2019). Nonlinearity and amplification in cochlear responses to single and multi-tone stimuli. *Hearing research*, 377, 271–281. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heares.2019.04.001>

7. Hudspeth, A.J., Corey, D.P., 1977. Sensitivity, polarity, and conductance change in the response of vertebrate hair cells to controlled mechanical stimuli. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 74, 2407–2411. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.74.6.2407>
8. Karavitaki, K.D., Mountain, D.C., 2007. Imaging electrically evoked micromechanical motion within the organ of Corti of the excised gerbil cochlea. *Biophys. J.* 92, 3294–3316. <https://doi.org/10.1529/biophysj.106.083634>
9. Meenderink, S. W. F., & Dong, W. (2022). Organ of Corti vibrations are dominated by longitudinal motion in vivo. *Communications biology*, 5(1), 1285. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-022-04234-7>
10. Motallebzadeh, H., Soons, J. A. M., & Puria, S. (2018). Cochlear amplification and tuning depend on the cellular arrangement within the organ of Corti. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 115(22), 5762–5767. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1720979115>
11. Russell, I. J., & Nilsen, K. E. (1997). The location of the cochlear amplifier: spatial representation of a single tone on the guinea pig basilar membrane. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 94(6), 2660–2664. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.94.6.2660>
12. Shera, C. A., & Altoè, A. (2023). Otoacoustic emissions reveal the micromechanical role of organ-of-Corti cytoarchitecture in cochlear amplification. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 120(41), e2305921120. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2305921120>
13. Zagadou, B. F., Barbone, P. E., & Mountain, D. C. (2020). Significance of the Microfluidic Flow Inside the Organ of Corti. *Journal of biomechanical engineering*, 142(8), 081009. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4046637>
14. Zhou, W., Jabeen, T., Sabha, S., Becker, J., & Nam, J. H. (2022). Deiters Cells Act as Mechanical Equalizers for Outer Hair Cells. *The Journal of neuroscience : the official journal of the Society for Neuroscience*, 42(44), 8361–8372. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.2417-21.2022>
15. Zosuls, A., Rupprecht, L. C., & Mountain, D. C. (2021). Inner hair cell stereocilia displacement in response to focal stimulation of the basilar membrane in the ex vivo gerbil cochlea. *Hearing research*, 412, 108372. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heares.2021.108372>

COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Online Forum]

[C Elliot Strimbu]: These are very interesting results and the data presented in Figures 2 and 3 look very nice. I have a few questions about the preparation and technique.

1. Since these experiments are performed on an in situ preparation I would assume that there is no endocochlear potential. Have you ever tried to restore the EP or apply transepithelial electrical stimulation to simulate the EP? Do you think this would make a difference in the mechanical responses you measure?
 2. Have you tried blocking electromotility by adding salicylate to the extracellular solution or blocking transduction with, say transduction channel blockers such as the aminoglycosides? I just wonder what the contributions of the active process(es) is to the motion you observe.
 3. Have you ever tried to measure the motion of the tectorial membrane? Perhaps by placing reflective beads on it? This may not be so relevant to the data presented here, but the motion of the TM remains somewhat mysterious. There is a typo in the last sentence of the Figure 2 caption. It says "Panel C and C...".
- Good luck with the experiments,

[Aleksandrs Zosuls]:

Thank you Elliot.

- 1) You are correct, there is no endocochlear potential. I have not yet tried to restore it or simulate the EP. Domenico electrically evoked the outer hair cells, her results were quite different than ours. I do think that restoring the EP would make a difference since it may restore some of the active processes. This would depend on the overall health of the cochlear partition.
- 2) I have not tried to block electromotility. If I get the opportunity to continue this research, we will certainly aim to perform these experiments where we investigate passive and active processes in the same preparation.
- 3) I do have measurements of motion of the tectorial membrane. Stay tuned!

4) Thank you! I will correct the typo.

[Brian Frost]: Hi Aleks - Nice work, and very interesting method.

I was hoping you could provide some more details about the stimulation. How could you be sure contact was made? Once contact is made, more stiffness is measured if the probe is pushed "further in" to the BM (Olson + Mountain). I wonder if this could change your results.

I also am colorblind, and cannot read the RHS of Fig 1 at all. Sorry, I know Red/Green is generally high-contrast for most people, but I know others in the field are colorblind so it may be nice if you could change that (if it is sufficiently simple).

As a minor note, it is Deiters', not Deiter's (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Otto_DeitersLinks to an external site.)

It was nice seeing you, and your talk, at the conference!

[Aleksandrs Zosuls]: Thank you, Brian.

The establishment of contact was something that took a few cochleae to practice and one of the most challenging parts of the preparation. It was performed in a few steps. The first is using the microscope focus to find the bottom of the basilar membrane and then finding the probe tip. Using the focus knob micrometer I could get a rough sense of the distance and close it by running the motorized stage a distance less than the target. Once I was close, I would focus on the lower BM pectinate fibers which were very high contrast. Then I would step the motorized stage in small increments, typically 500 nm until I saw the slightest movement of the collagen fibers. The collagen fibers produce a bit of optical interference that results in a crosshatch pattern since they are at a bias. I learned to see a slight change in the interference fringes and knew that would be just in contact. The tympanic border cells on the scala tympani side of the basilar membrane are very compliant so the probe would push into them before making contact with the collagen fibers. The telltale sign of pushing in too deep would cause a visible upward (modiilar) bulge in the pillar cell head row directly above the probe. If this was visible, then the prep would be considered damaged at that point. I agree, if the probe advanced too deep into the basilar membrane there would be an increase in stiffness but also a change in the geometry of the cochlear partition. At the termination of the experiments, I would often drive the probe deep into the BM and watch the cells deform and move in response. It was way past physiological but informative and neat to watch structures bend and buckle.

I attribute the difference in signal to noise ratio between the different cochlear preparations to how well the probe was in contact.

In some cases if I didn't make contact and started an experiment, only a forward traveling wave would be resolvable from the data. I interpret this to mean that the probe was acting as a pressure source in close proximity to the BM and was exciting the cochlear partition by the typical differential pressure we expect from a stapes drive. Sorry that the figures are hard to interpret. I made the figures more color independent. Thank you for letting me know.

[Presentation discussion]

[John Hoon Nam]: Excellent talk, great talk, your information will be used in every computer model of ours. I have a quick clarifying question regarding your longitudinal space constant. Along which radial position was it measured, in the pillar cell top, first row outer hair cells, third row outer hair cells?

[Aleksandrs Zosuls]: That was measured in the pillar cell heads and which is the same as that in the inner hair cells, so that's where the space constant was measured there and I measured it outside of the region of the probe because the probe distorts the tissue locally.

[Jong Hoon Nam]: Have you measured the other rows longitudinal space constant along the other rows of outer hair cells? The longitudinal space constant?

[Aleksandrs Zosuls]: I have the data, but I have not looked at it yet. But I can get that to you. If people need data from this, I have TONs of data. I have this done at 5 or 6 focal planes and also, I repeated this in chinchilla so there are thousands of data points. Thanks!

[Unknown]: Hi very interesting presentation. I am interested in magnitude of up down motion. Well, you know probably you have controlled amplitude of the probe going up and down. How big is the sideways movement you have and ratios?

[Aleksandrs Zosuls]: Yes, the probe is typically moving either 200 nanometers or 400 nanometers peak which is kind of on the high end. Typically, you will see a peak about the uh at CF a resonance but off of CF you will see a transmission ratio of about .2 to .5 In other words if we put in 100 nanometers transverse we would see 20 or 50 nanometers and that is somewhat dependent on if we hit resonance or not of the organ of Corti.

[Paul Kolston]: Fantastic talk, in a finite difference model I did which I analyze which included things like individual outer hair cells and Deiter's cells and things, I found that local stimulation produced quite different response to stimulation from a normal travelling wave and I'm just wondering if you had any comments about how what your seeing might relate to the where you have actually a traveling wave stimulation. I'm talking about things like phase between the different parts of the organ.

[Aleksandrs Zosuls]: Yeah, I think the point probe does something, if I take the point probe and back it off of the bm 20-30 um it turns into a pressure source, and when you do that you don't see the reverse traveling wave, it disappears. The thought is that preferentially, the basilar membrane, the wave preferentially wants to travel forwards, but it can travel backwards if you have a high enough signal to noise ratio to see it, such that it makes it a lot more complicated if you think of distortion product otoacoustic emissions making people cry, you just might not be able to see the reverse traveling wave because it is so small and hard to see because it is mixed in with forward waves that are dominant.